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Review Article

**MICROPLASTICS AS AN EMERGING HUMAN HEALTH
RISK: MECHANISMS, EXPOSURE, AND CLINICAL
EVIDENCE****Dr Asif Rasheed, Hadiqa Bushra Awesi, Farzeen Ajmal Younus**

Department of Pharmacology, Deccan School of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India

Abstract:

Microplastics (MPs) refer to plastic particles <5 mm in size, have gained growing attention pervasive across environmental compartments such as air, soil, and aquatic systems. Human exposure primarily occurs via ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact with MPs now detected in various biological specimens such as blood, placenta, lung tissue, and cardiovascular tissue. Evidence indicates that MPs can move across biological membranes, undergo systemic distribution, and build up within tissues, raising concern for organ-specific toxicity. Mechanisms implicated in microplastic-induced pathology include oxidative stress, inflammation, epithelial barrier disruption, cellular injury, mitochondrial dysfunction, autophagy dysregulation, and thrombogenic effects. Emerging clinical observations link microplastic burden with cardiovascular disease severity, respiratory disorders, and inflammatory conditions, though causality remains incompletely defined. Advances in detection methodologies, including microscopy, spectroscopy, and mass spectrometric techniques, have supported identification and characterization of MPs in human samples. Prevention strategies focus on reducing plastic use, modifying dietary and personal habits, and improving water treatment and filtration systems. Overall, the growing evidence underscores microplastics as a pressing environmental health concern requiring further mechanistic, epidemiological, and regulatory investigation.

Keywords: Microplastics; Human health; Exposure pathways; Cardiovascular toxicity; Respiratory toxicity; Oxidative stress; Autophagy; Inflammation; Nanoplastics

Corresponding author:**Hadiqa Bushra Awesi,**

Department of Pharmacology,

Deccan School of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India

Email-id- bushraawesi@gmail.com

Contact Details- 9063702846

QR CODE

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INTRODUCTION:

Microplastics (MPs) are water-insoluble synthetic particles or polymer matrices originating from either primary or secondary sources. These particles vary widely in shape, ranging from regular to irregular forms, and typically measure between 1 μm and 5 mm in size.¹ As an emerging global pollutant, MPs persist in the environment due to their slow degradation rates and have been shown to exert diverse adverse effects, including reproductive toxicity, inflammation, carcinogenicity, and mutagenicity.² Particles smaller than 1 μm are classified as nanoplastics. Unlike engineered nanomaterials, microplastics represent a heterogeneous mixture of plastic particles with diverse shapes and physicochemical properties, and their increasing presence is a growing concern for human health.³ This review summarizes the effects of microplastics on human health, the determinants of their toxicity, and the underlying mechanisms. Microplastics have been detected in various human biological samples, including faeces, sputum, saliva, blood, and placental tissue. Exposure to microplastics has been associated with a range of health conditions, including cancer, as well as intestinal, pulmonary, cardiovascular, infectious, and inflammatory diseases. The potential effects of microplastic exposure during pregnancy and the maternal period are also discussed. Current remediation approaches include coagulation, membrane bioreactors, sand filtration, adsorption, photocatalytic degradation, electrocoagulation, and magnetic separation. Control strategies primarily focus on reducing plastic use, promoting behavioral changes, and encouraging the adoption of biodegradable plastics.⁴ Microplastics can enter the human body through inhalation and ingestion, potentially causing adverse health effects. A useful comparison can be drawn with particulate air pollution, where small particles (<2.5 μm), such as those from diesel exhaust, can cross cell membranes, trigger oxidative stress and inflammation, and increase the risk of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, as well as lung cancer. This similarity highlights the need for further research to understand the potential health risks of microplastic exposure.⁵

All plastic materials, including synthetic textiles, can generate secondary microplastics that disperse throughout the environment. For instance, fiber deposition during meals may result in higher exposure than consuming mussels, with estimates of up to 68,415 particles per person per year compared to 4,620 particles. Oral intake from drinking water and seafood is estimated at 34,254 particles per person per year, while consumption of terrestrial animal products may lead to exposure of around 15,381 particles per day (~5,614,065 particles per year). Airborne exposure in China has been

estimated at 3,360 particles per day (~1,226,400 particles per year). These findings indicate that most of the population is environmentally exposed to microplastics. Occupational exposure is less frequent but occurs among workers in plastics or textile industries, where chronic exposure to high concentrations of airborne microplastics—often due to insufficient protective measures—can lead to adverse health effects, including airway and lung diseases.⁶

Exposure Of Microplastics**Environmental Distribution and Entry of Microplastics**

Microplastics enter the environment through multiple pathways and contaminate major ecological compartments such as soil, air, and water. From these sources, they interact with plants, animals, and humans through several routes of exposure, primarily contact, ingestion, inhalation, and entanglement.^[7]

Exposure Pathways in Plants

Plants are exposed mainly through contaminated soil, irrigation water, and atmospheric deposition, enabling microplastics to accumulate on plant surfaces or be taken up by root systems.^[7]

Exposure Pathways in Animals

Animals encounter microplastics through soil or sediment interaction, contaminated water, air, and food sources, with exposure occurring via direct contact, inhalation of airborne particles, ingestion of polluted feed or prey, and in some cases physical entanglement.^[7]

Human Exposure to Microplastics

Humans experience the broadest exposure spectrum, receiving microplastics from soil/dust, air, water, food, plants, animals, and various consumer or personal care products. Human exposure predominantly occurs through ingestion (contaminated food and drinking water), inhalation (airborne microplastics), and dermal contact.^[7]

Major Human Exposure Routes

The main exposure pathways through which microplastics can enter the human body include oral intake, inhalation, and dermal contact. Oral intake represents one of the most significant routes, as microplastics have been detected in drinking water, various foods (including seafood), and food packaging materials, and may even be ingested by infants through plastic baby feeding products. Inhalation of airborne microplastics provides another route of exposure, especially in indoor environments where synthetic fibers and particulate matter accumulate. In addition, skin contact can contribute to microplastic exposure through personal care products containing microbeads and through frequent handling of polymer-based consumer items such as mobile phone cases.^[8]

Ingestion, Inhalation, and Dermal Exposure

Ingestion is a major route, arising from the consumption of contaminated drinking water, various food items such as honey and beverages, and marine or plant-derived foods through the trophic transfer of MPs. Exposure may also occur through the use of personal care products—including toothpaste, face washes, scrubs, and soaps—which contribute to both oral and dermal uptake.

In addition, MPs can enter the body via dermal contact with contaminated soil, water, or airborne fallout, as well as through particulate deposition on exposed meals. Inhalation of airborne MPs represents another significant route of exposure.^[8]

Microplastics in Aquatic Organisms and Seafood

The capacity of microplastics (MPs) to move from the digestive system into other tissues of aquatic organisms has heightened concerns regarding the safety of seafood. While numerous studies on wild fish have quantified MP accumulation in the gastrointestinal tract, comparatively few have examined their presence in edible muscle tissues.⁷

Prevention of Microplastic Exposure

Reducing exposure to microplastics starts with lowering the amount of plastic we use every day. Avoid heating food in plastic, since heat increases chemical leaching. Use glass, ceramic, or stainless steel containers for microwaving or storing leftovers instead of plastic.

Keeping living spaces clean also helps, because household dust can contain microplastics. Vacuuming is more effective than sweeping for removing dust and preventing particles from being stirred into the air.

Diet plays a role as well. Processed foods tend to contain higher levels of microplastics, so choosing fresh, less-processed options may reduce intake. Avoid storing food in plastic containers for long periods, and try to avoid canned products with plastic or BPA-based linings. Filtering tap water adds an extra layer of protection.

Personal care products and household items can contribute too. Some cosmetics contain microplastics, and synthetic clothing sheds microfibers during washing. Washing clothes only when necessary can help reduce microfiber release into water systems. HEPA filters can also capture a portion of airborne microplastics indoors, although the smallest particles may still pass through.

Be mindful when consuming seafood, especially filter-feeding animals like oysters and mussels, as they can accumulate microplastics in their digestive systems. Microplastics can also move up the marine food chain, and many can carry harmful chemicals. Finally, switching to reusable water bottles, coffee cups, takeout containers, and shopping bags helps

cut down on single-use plastics and lowers potential exposure overall.

Effect on cardiovascular system

Recent research shows that Microplastics are capable of accumulating in cardiomyocytes (heart muscle cells), triggering oxidative stress and contributing to Microplastics can induce oxidative stress, cardiac injury, and fibrosis. Their presence has also been detected in atherosclerotic plaques, including those in the carotid arteries, where they have been associated with an increased risk of stroke and increased mortality. Similarly, microplastics have been associated with coronary artery atherosclerosis, and elevated microplastic concentrations appear to correlate with the severity of coronary artery disease (CAD).^[10]

This chapter explores how microplastics are produced, how humans are exposed to them, and the pathways through which exposure leads to cellular injury they enter the body. It also outlines the The toxic effects of microplastics occur via multiple mechanisms, including oxidative stress, DNA damage, inflammation, and immune dysregulation—through which microplastics contribute to disease development across various organs. Particular focus is given to cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), contributing to cardiovascular diseases, which continue to be the leading cause of death worldwide. The chapter further highlights recent studies investigating the presence of microplastics in cardiovascular tissues and their association with CVD severity. Despite these emerging links, a direct causal relationship between microplastic burden and the clinical severity of disease in humans has not yet been conclusively established.^[10]

Microplastics have been shown to influence cardiovascular function through multiple pathological mechanisms. They may promote platelet aggregation and thrombosis, increasing the likelihood of clot formation. At the cellular level, microplastics can induce membrane damage and trigger autophagy as a protective response. They also contribute to oxidative stress and inflammation, which are known drivers of cardiac injury. In addition, microplastics can impair mitochondrial integrity and disrupt energy metabolism within cardiac cells. Developmental studies indicate that exposure to microplastics may interfere with normal atrioventricular valve formation.^[9]

Nanoplastics (NPs) are increasingly present in the environment, raising concerns about human exposure and potential cardiovascular effects. In this study, polystyrene nanoplastics (PS-NPs) of 100 nm and 500 nm were tested on human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) to evaluate their

interaction and impact on autophagy. Both particle sizes associated with HUVECs in a dose- and time-dependent manner, with 500 nm particles remaining on the cell surface and 100 nm particles being internalized and accumulating in the cytoplasm. Exposure to 25 µg/mL of 500 nm PS-NPs increased lactate dehydrogenase release, indicating cell injury. In contrast, internalized 100 nm PS-NPs caused membrane damage and activated autophagy, while also impairing autophagic flux. Overall, the study suggests that smaller PS-NPs pose greater intracellular risk and trigger size-dependent cellular responses.^[11]

Studies investigating the cardiovascular impacts of microplastics in humans have primarily used human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) in vitro models. In these experiments, polystyrene nanoparticles (PS-NPs) of 100 nm and 500 nm in size were introduced at concentrations ranging from 5 to 100 µg/mL over varying exposure periods. The results demonstrated that 500 nm PS-NPs tended to bind to the outer surface of endothelial cell membranes, while 100 nm particles were more readily internalized and accumulated in the cytoplasm. Exposure to 25 µg/mL of 500 nm PS-NPs significantly increased the release of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), indicating cellular injury. Meanwhile, the 100 nm nanoparticles induced marked membrane damage and triggered autophagy, including autophagosome formation. These findings suggest that nanoparticle size influences cellular uptake and toxicity, with smaller particles exhibiting deeper intracellular effects.^[9]

Recent evidence shows that microplastics can accumulate within various components of the cardiovascular system. In blood vessels, microplastics have been detected at concentrations of approximately 1.6 µg/mL, with particle sizes greater than 700 nm. These particles include polymers such as PET, PE, PS, EPS, ABS, and PMMA, suggesting widespread polymeric contamination within circulating blood ⁽¹⁴⁾. Microplastics have also been found in thrombi, where an average of 87 particles per sample were identified, ranging from 2.1 µm to 26 µm in size. These particles appeared block-shaped and were observed in colors such as yellow, green, and red, originating from polymers including LDPE and pigments such as chromium oxide and phthalocyanine ⁽¹⁵⁾. In venous tissue, an average of 20 particles (approximately 14.99 ± 17.18 particles/g of tissue) were detected, with sizes ranging between 16 µm and 1074 µm and presenting as fragments and fibers made of alkyd resin, poly(vinyl propionate), and nylon-EVA materials ⁽¹⁶⁾. Microplastics have also been identified in heart tissue, with particle sizes ranging from 20 µm to 500 µm, involving polymers such as PET, PVC, and

PMMA ⁽¹⁷⁾. Together, these findings indicate that microplastics are not confined to the respiratory or digestive pathways but can circulate and lodge within cardiovascular structures, raising concern about potential impacts on vascular health. ^[14]

Effect on Respiratory system

Human exposure to airborne microparticles largely depends on their size. These particles are generally grouped into four ranges: larger than 10 micrometers, smaller than 10 micrometers, smaller than 2.5 micrometers, and ultrafine particles smaller than 0.1 micrometers. When inhaled, the larger particles tend to get trapped in the upper airways, while the smaller ones can reach deeper into the bronchioles. The tiniest particles are able to travel all the way down into the alveoli.

Evidence from human biomonitoring has shown that plastic particles can accumulate in lung tissues, confirming that inhaled microplastics can deposit and persist there. Prolonged exposure to these airborne particles has been associated with respiratory problems, including conditions such as asthma and pneumoconiosis.

Fibrous particles released from synthetic fabrics are also widely present in the air and can easily be inhaled. Many of these fibers are captured by the fluid lining of the lungs, but some can evade the body's natural clearance systems. Inhalation is considered one of the main pathways through which humans take in microparticles, especially due to their small size, which allows airborne microplastics to be breathed in directly.^[12]

1. Disruption of the epithelial barrier

Pulmonary surfactants are essential for keeping the alveoli open, reducing surface tension, clearing mucus, and helping remove inhaled particles and microbes. Microplastics can disturb the structure and behavior of these surfactants, causing the surfactant film to collapse and weakening the lung's natural defenses. Polystyrene particles, for example, can bind to surfactant lipids, change surface tension, and generate reactive oxygen species that damage surfactant membranes. Microplastics also reduce the integrity of epithelial tight junctions and impair repair processes, making the barrier more permeable. As a result, allergens and toxins can enter deeper tissues more easily, increasing vulnerability contributing to respiratory conditions, including asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)

2. Cellular toxicity and injury

Microplastics can be taken up by lung epithelial cells, and their entry depends on characteristics such as size and surface charge. Smaller and positively charged particles are internalized more efficiently and can cause structural changes, cell death, and

damage to alveolar and bronchial tissues. Studies in animals and cell cultures show that long-term exposure can injure lung tissue and contribute to the development or worsening of respiratory diseases. While lower concentrations may sometimes show minimal toxicity, higher doses often reduce cell viability and trigger apoptotic pathways, influenced by factors like polymer type, aging of the particles, and the contaminants they carry.

3. Inflammation and oxidative stress

Exposure to microplastics can activate airway epithelial cells to release pro-inflammatory cytokines, driving inflammation in both experimental animals and cell-based studies.

Increased inflammatory markers are associated with asthma, airway remodeling, fibrosis, emphysema, and even lung cancer. Microplastics also disturb redox balance by generating reactive oxygen species and reducing antioxidant defenses. This oxidative stress promotes inflammation, tissue injury, and may participate in chronic respiratory diseases including asthma, COPD, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).^[13]

Microplastics have also been documented within the human respiratory system. In lung tissue samples, an average of 31 particles were identified per sample, ranging in size from approximately 1.6 to 16.8 μm and appearing mainly as fragments and fibers. These particles displayed a range of colors, such as transparent and white, blue, grey, yellow, brown, and orange, and were composed of polymers such as polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), cotton fibers, PVC, cellulose acetate (CA), polyamide (PA), polystyrene (PS), and polyurethane (PU)⁽¹⁹⁾. Microplastics were similarly detected in lung granulomatous nodules, where an average of 65 particles larger than 20 μm were reported. These particles were predominantly fibrous and appeared in purple, blue, transparent, yellow, and red, with polymer types including cotton, PA, polyester, denim fibers, and phenoxy resin⁽²⁰⁾. Additional lung tissue analyses revealed around 39 particles per sample, ranging from 12 to 2475 μm in size and presenting as fibers, fragments, or films. The detected polymers included PP, PET, resins, PE, PTFE, PS, PAN, PES, PMMA, PUR, SEBS, and TPE⁽²¹⁾. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that microplastics of diverse sizes, shapes, colors, and polymer compositions are able to reach and accumulate within different regions of the human lung.

Techniques for Detecting Microplastics^[18]

Detection Workflow in Humans and Organisms

The detection of microplastics in biological systems follows a standardized multi-step workflow designed to separate synthetic particles from complex biological matrices. The process begins with **sample collection**, which may involve tissues

(e.g., lung, liver, colon), fluids (blood, stool, urine), lavage, or biopsies. Following collection, samples undergo **digestion or cleanup**, where organic material is removed using chemical or enzymatic treatments without degrading the plastic components. The resulting material is subjected to **physical separation**, often driven by filtration or density separation to isolate particles according to their size and buoyancy. Finally, **chemical identification** techniques verify the polymeric nature of the particles. Using this workflow, microplastics have been reliably detected in marine organisms and across several human specimen types, including vascular tissue, lung tissue, gastrointestinal content, blood, and feces, confirming that humans are both exposed to and capable of internalizing microplastics.

Microscopy-Based Screening

Microscopy serves as the primary screening tool for initial particle recognition. **Stereo or optical microscopy** allows visual sorting of suspected microplastics based on morphological descriptors such as color, geometry (fibers, fragments, films, spheres), and approximate size. While optical microscopy aids in preliminary classification, higher-resolution approaches such as **scanning electron microscopy (SEM)** provide detailed topographical analysis of particle surfaces and fracture patterns. When SEM is coupled with **energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS)**, elemental composition can be assessed, supporting differentiation between synthetic polymers and natural organic particulates. Microscopy-based approaches have been widely used in ecological studies of microplastics in marine organisms and more recently applied to human tissues and blood samples as evidence of internal exposure.

Spectroscopic Polymer Identification

Microscopy alone cannot confirm polymer composition, therefore **spectroscopic techniques** are considered the analytical gold standard for polymer identification. **Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) microspectroscopy** and **Raman microspectroscopy** generate molecular vibrational spectra that serve as chemical fingerprints for specific polymer types. These instruments can distinguish plastics from natural cellulose, proteins, minerals, and pigments. Micro-FTIR imaging platforms further allow automated mapping of particles, classifying particle types and quantifying their abundance. Raman microspectroscopy offers superior spatial resolution—extending its capability to smaller particles including sub-10 μm ranges—and can detect highly pigmented or dark materials that FTIR may struggle with. Advanced spectral libraries and machine learning tools have increased

throughput, enabling large-scale surveys in environmental and biomedical research.

Thermal and Mass Spectrometric Analysis

Thermal degradation approaches provide an alternative means of assessing microplastics within complex biological matrices. Techniques such as **pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS)** and **thermal-desorption GC-MS** operate by thermally decomposing polymers into characteristic volatile breakdown products which can then be separated and analyzed by mass spectrometry. These techniques generate quantitative data on polymer mass and composition and are particularly advantageous for samples rich in nanoplastics or for matrices in which particles cannot be visually separated. However, thermal analysis does not preserve particle morphology, meaning that size distribution, shape, and particle count cannot be directly obtained. As a result, thermal-mass spectrometric methods are frequently used alongside microscopic and spectroscopic techniques to achieve comprehensive characterization of microplastic burden in biological samples.

REFERENCES:

1. The potential impact of nano- and microplastics on human health: Understanding human health risks
Winiarska E, Jutel M, Zemelka-Wiacek M. The potential impact of nano- and microplastics on human health: understanding human health risks. *Environmental Research*. 2024;118535. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2024.118535.
2. Microplastics are associated with elevated atherosclerotic risk and increased vascular complexity in acute coronary syndrome patients
Yang Y, Feng Z, Jiang Z, Du Z, Liu S, Zhang M, et al. Microplastics are associated with elevated atherosclerotic risk and increased vascular complexity in acute coronary syndrome patients. *Particle and Fibre Toxicology*. 2024;21:34. doi:10.1186/s12989-024-00598-7.
3. Potential Health Impact of Microplastics: A Review of Environmental Distribution, Human Exposure, and Toxic Effects.
Li Y, Tao L, Wang Q, Wang F, Li G, Song M. *Environ Health*. 2023;1(4):249–257. doi:10.1021/envhealth.3c00052
4. Microplastic sources, formation, toxicity and remediations: a review
Li C, Busquets R, Campos LC. Microplastic sources, formation, toxicity and remediations: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*. 2023;21:2129-2169. doi:10.1007/s10311-023-01554y.
5. Microplastics and human health
Vethaak AD, Legler J. Microplastics and human health. *Science*. 2021;371(6530):672-674. doi:10.1126/science.abe5041.
6. Microplastics and human health: Integrating pharmacokinetics
Prata JC. Microplastics and human health: integrating pharmacokinetics. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*. 2023;53(16):1489-1511. doi:10.1080/10643389.2023.2195798.
7. Microplastics in eviscerated flesh and excised organs of dried fish.
Karami A, Goliškardi A, Ho YB, Larat V, Salamatinia B. *Sci Rep*. 2017;7:5473. doi:10.1038/s41598-017-05828-6.
8. Microplastics Exposure Routes and Toxicity Studies to Ecosystems: An Overview
Enyoh CE, Shafea L, Verla AW, Verla EN, Qingyue W, Chowdhury T, et al. Microplastics exposure routes and toxicity studies to ecosystems: an overview. *Environ Anal Health Toxicol*. 2020;35(1):e2020004. doi:10.5620/eAHT.e2020004.
9. The potential impacts of micro-and-nano plastics on various organ systems in humans (2024)
Ali N, Katsouli J, Marczylo EL, Gant TW, Wright S, Bernardino de la Serna J. The potential impacts of micro- and nano-plastics on various organ systems in humans. *EBioMedicine*. 2024;99:104901.
10. Impact of Microplastics on Human Health
Kumar G, Duggal B, Banerjee P. Impact of microplastics on human health. In: Bala K, Roqueira F, Barhaba GK, Weichgrebe D, editors. *Occurrence, detection, and fate of microplastics in freshwater ecosystems*. Springer; 2025. P. 221-240.
11. Size-dependent effects of polystyrene nanoplastics on autophagy response in human umbilical vein endothelial cells.
Lu YY, Li H, Ren H, Zhang X, Huang F, Zhang D, Huang Q, Zhang X. *J Hazard Mater*. 2022;421:126770. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126770.
12. Effect of microplastics deposition on human lung airways: A review with computational benefits and challenges.
Saha SC, Saha G. . *Heliyon*. 2024 Jan 11;10(2):e24355. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24355.
13. Microplastics, potential threat to patients with lung diseases.
Lu K, Zhan D, Fang Y, Li L, Chen G, Chen S, Wang L. *Front Toxicol*. 2022 Sep 28;4:958414. doi:10.3389/ftox.2022.958414.
14. Detection of microplastics in human tissues and organs: A scoping review.
Roslan NS, Lee YY, Ibrahim YS, Anuar ST, Yusof KMK, Lai LA, Brentnall T. *J Glob Health*. 2024 Aug 23.

15. Wu D, Feng Y, Wang R, Jiang J, Guan Q, Yang X, Wei H, Xia Y, Luo Y. Pigment microparticles and microplastics found in human thrombi based on Raman spectral evidence. *J Adv Res.* 2023 Jul;49:141–150. doi:10.1016/j.jare.2022.09.004.
16. Rotchell JM, Jenner LC, Chapman E, Bennett RT, Bolanle IO, Loubani M, Sadofsky L, Hobkirk J, Palmer TM. Detection of microplastics in human saphenous vein tissue using μ FTIR: A pilot study. *PLoS One.* 2023 Feb 1;18(2):e0280594. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0280594.
17. Yang Y, Xie E, Du Z, Peng Z, Han Z, Li L, Zhao R, Qin Y, Xue M, Li F, Hua K, Yang X. Detection of various microplastics in patients undergoing cardiac surgery. *Environ Sci Technol.* 2023 Jul 13;57(30):10911–10918. doi:10.1021/acs.est.2c07179.
18. Foster B. Methods for microplastics detection. *Technology Networks – Applied Sciences.* 2024 Dec 13.
19. Amato-Lourenço LF, Carvalho-Oliveira R, Ribeiro Junior G, Galvão LDS, Ando RA, Mauad T. Presence of airborne microplastics in human lung tissue. *J Hazard Mater.* 2021 Aug 15;416:126124. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126124.
20. An emerging role of microplastics in the etiology of lung ground glass nodules. *Environ Sci Eur.* 2022;34:25. doi:10.1186/s12302-022-00614-3.
21. Jenner LC, Rotchell JM, Bennett RT, Cowen M, Tentzeris V, Sadofsky LR. Detection of microplastics in human lung tissue using μ FTIR spectroscopy. *Sci Total Environ.* 2022 Jul 20;831:154907. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154907.